

Ion Exchange Selectivity of Monovalent and Bivalent Inorganic and Organic Ions towards Tris-Trimethylene Diamine Co(III) Exchanged Amberlite IRC-50

J. L. DAS KANUNGO and G. N. SARKAR

Department of Chemistry, University of North Bengal,
Dist. Darjeeling-734 430

Manuscript received 5 March 1983, revised 15 September 1983, accepted 11 February 1984

IN continuation of our earlier investigation¹ on the ion exchange behaviour of alkali metal ions in Amberlite IRC-50, we report the desorption characteristics of tris-trimethylene diamine Co(III), $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$, from $\text{Na}-\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3-\text{IRC-50}$ by hydrogen, alkaline earth metal, quaternary ammonium and alkane diammonium ions of varying size and shape. An attempt has been made to correlate the relative selectivities of the bivalent inorganic ions for the resin surface with the reciprocal of the Debye Hückel ion-size parameter, a^0 .

Experimental

The characteristics of the resin and the experimental details for studying exchange equilibrium are the same as reported earlier^{1,2}. The exchange capacity of the H-resin was found to be 1020 meq/100 g dry resin (dried at 105°) by $\text{NaOH}-\text{HCl}$ method while the maximum uptake of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ on to Na-form of the resin corresponds to 704 meq/100 g. All the reagents used were of AnalaR quality.

Results and Discussion

The exchange isotherms of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from $\text{Na}-\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3-\text{IRC-50}$ by alkaline earth metal cations and H^+ are shown in Fig. 1. Desorption increases³ with the crystallographic radius of the bivalent ions. The exchangeability of H^+ , however, is found to be greater than the bivalent ions. This peculiar behaviour of H^+ has been explained by assuming H^+ to be present as a bare proton in exchange reactions as a consequence of which it has a higher accessibility to the exchange sites³.

Fig. 1. Exchange isotherms of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from $\text{Na}-\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3-\text{IRC-50}$ by monovalent and bivalent inorganic ions.

The distribution and selectivity coefficients of the exchanging ions have been calculated as in our previous paper³ and recorded in Table 1. In an

TABLE 1—DESORPTION CHARACTERISTICS OF $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ FROM $\text{Na}-\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3-\text{IRC-50}$ AGAINST VARIOUS INORGANIC AND ORGANIC IONS

Electrolyte used	Concentration of electrolyte M	Distribution coefficient	Selectivity coefficient
HCl	2.0×10^{-3}	364.28	77.23
	4.0×10^{-3}	168.8	43.76
MgCl_2	4.0×10^{-3}	11.14	1.74
	10.0×10^{-3}	8.95	1.90
CaCl_2	4.0×10^{-3}	11.47	1.84
	10.0×10^{-3}	9.47	2.18
SrCl_2	4.0×10^{-3}	11.85	1.96
	10.0×10^{-3}	9.76	2.34
BaCl_2	4.0×10^{-3}	12.39	2.11
	10.0×10^{-3}	10.0	2.49
$(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NCl}$	2.0×10^{-1}	0.67	0.04
	6.0×10^{-1}	0.62	0.05
$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NBr}$	1.0×10^{-1}	0.60	0.027
	2.0×10^{-1}	0.60	0.032
$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_7)_4\text{NI}$	1.0×10^{-1}	0.30	0.011
	2.0×10^{-1}	0.37	0.017
DDTABr	1.0×10^{-3}	4.54	0.16
	2.0×10^{-3}	3.03	0.14
CTABr	1.0×10^{-3}	42.13	3.37
	2.0×10^{-3}	32.78	3.07
CPCI	1.0×10^{-3}	53.44	4.54
	2.0×10^{-3}	38.33	3.31
EDA	1.0×10^{-3}	16.20	1.80
	2.0×10^{-3}	13.21	1.72
PrDA	1.0×10^{-3}	11.42	1.02
	2.0×10^{-3}	10.90	1.27

attempt to correlate the relative affinities of the desorbing alkaline earth metal chlorides for the resin matrix with their sizes, plot of \log (selectivity coefficient) against the reciprocal of the Debye Hückel parameter, a^0 , i.e. the distance of the closest approach between the counter ion and the fixed ionic group, has been made (Fig. 2). This plot, however, is according to the model of Pauley⁵ which assumes

Fig. 2. Correlation of selectivity coefficient with the Debye Hückel parameter, a^0 , of the alkaline earth metal chlorides.

that the electrostatic interaction between the counter ions and the fixed ionic groups is the major factor in ion exchange. Interestingly, the parameter shows linear relation suggesting that $\frac{1}{a_0}$ may be utilised for correlating the relative selectivities of the bivalent ions for the resin surface.

The release of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from the resin by mono-valent and bivalent organic ions are presented in Fig. 3. It can be seen that the amounts of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ exchanged by $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$, $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}^+$ and $(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_4\text{N}^+$ are very small compared to the inorganic ions and the exchange is inversely related to the size of the ions. Barrer *et al*⁶ measured the extents of exchange in a near-faujasite (Linde Sieve X) from concentrated solutions of various methyl and ethylammonium halides and ammonium chloride and

Fig. 3. Exchange isotherms of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from $\text{Na}-\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3-\text{IRC}-50$ by tetraalkylammonium, alkane diammonium and long-chain surface active ions.

reported an ion sieve exclusion of $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}^+$, while the methylammonium cations showed upper limits of exchange which decreased as the number of methyl groups increased. Barrer and Meier^{7,8} extended this work to the synthetic zeolite, Linde Sieve A, for the ions $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_x\text{NH}_3^+$ ($x=0, 1, 2, 3$ and 5), and also to $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_4\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)\text{NH}_3^+$, $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{NH}^+$, $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$ and $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}^+$ and noted that ion sieve exclusion was demonstrated for the last two cations, and a steric effect which is not of an ion sieve character was also operative. Because of its rigid non-swelling framework, exchange in Amberlite IRC-50 resin also is likely to be influenced by steric and space factors. Since ion-exchange inherently requires a "two-way traffic" and cannot take place in a "one-way street"⁹, the size of the tetraalkylammonium ions may be too big to pass another ion into the narrow cavities of the resin matrix and the results can be explained in terms of ion sieve action and steric factors as mentioned above for zeolites.

With the long-chain surface active ions such as dodecyltrimethylammonium (DDTA), cetyltri-

thylammonium (CTA) and cetylpyridinium (CP), the extent of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ exchange increases with chain length. Slade *et al*¹⁰ recently reported that cetylpyridinium ions when adsorbed onto vermiculite, a semi-swelling and high charge clay mineral, stand at about 57° to the silicate surface with their polar groups towards the surface, forming close-packed arrays. A similar conclusion with respect to the orientation of various alkylammonium ions was made by Theng¹¹ who studied the adsorption of these cations on highly charged synthetic near-faujasite. Due to the high exchange capacity (1020 meq/100 g) of Amberlite IRC-50, the resin has a high charge density surface and so an inclined orientation of the long-chain surface active ions with their charged ends towards the resin surface and the carbon chain oriented away from it seems probable. Since the charge ends of DDTA^+ and CTA^+ are the same, the increase in the readiness and the extent to which the organic cation is adsorbed as its size increases is due to the increase in the magnitude of the van der Waals forces, presumably due to the difference in the length of the carbon chain. This would suggest that van der Waals interactions between adjacent individual alkyl chains are more important than those operating between the alkyl chains and the resin surface¹¹.

The desorption of alkane diammonium ions like ethane diammonium (EDA) and 1,3-propane diammonium (PrDA), however, presents a higher exchange of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from the resin compared to the other organic ions studied, although an inverse relation was observed between the maximum exchange and the molecular weight. Due to their short-chain structure and double charge sites, these compounds probably experience less steric hindrance and an important contribution of van der Waals interaction causes the higher affinity of the alkane diammonium ions. A similar decrease in the maximum exchange with increasing molecular weight of the alkane diammonium ions was observed in Zeolite X by Vansant and Vanhoof¹² and has been attributed to the space requirement of the ions and the difficulties of packing of these organic ions in Zeolite framework. An X-ray study of the montmorillonite-alkane diammonium ion systems described by Fripiat *et al*¹³ reveals that the organic ions are adsorbed with their shorter axis perpendicular to the clay surface. However, since no data are available as to the surface area of the resin, definite orientation predictions of the adsorbed alkane diammonium ions cannot be drawn from the experimental isotherms, although it seems probable that the molecules lie flat on the adsorbent surface.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (G. N. S.) is indebted to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Teacher Fellowship.

References

1. G. N. SARKAR and J. L. DAS KANUNGO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 358.
2. J. L. DAS KANUNGO and S. K. CHAKRAVARTI, *Kolloid Z. and Z. Polym.*, 1972, **250**, 891.
3. C. KRISHNAMOORTHY and R. OVERSTREET, *Soil Sci.*, 1950, **69**, 41.
4. R. H. STOKES and R. A. ROBINSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1870.
5. J. L. PAULRY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 1422.
6. R. M. BARRER, W. BUSER and W. F. GRUTTER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1956, **39**, 518.
7. R. M. BARRER and W. M. MEIER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1958, **54**, 1074.
8. R. M. BARRER and W. M. MEIER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1959, **55**, 130.
9. F. HEFFERICH, "Ion Exchange", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962, p. 186.
10. P. G. SLADE, M. RAUPACH and W. W. EMERSON, *Clays and Clay Miner.*, 1978, **26**, 125.
11. B. K. G. THENG, *New Zealand J. Sci.*, 1971, **14**, 1026.
12. E. F. VANSANT and L. VANHOOF, *J. Royal Netherlands Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **97**, 191.
13. J. J. FRIPIAT, A. SERVAIS and A. LEONARD, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1962, **3**, 617.

Densities and Excess Volumes for Four Binary Mixtures of Ethyl Acetate with Toluene, Ethyl Benzene, Carbon Tetrachloride and Chloroform at 303.15 K

S. L. OSWAL* and M. V. RATHNAM

Department of Chemistry, South Gujarat University,
Surat-395 007

*Manuscript received 1 March 1983, revised 25 August 1983,
accepted 3 December 1983*

IN continuation of our earlier studies^{1,2} on molecular interactions between components of binary mixtures of esters with polar and non-polar solvents, we report the densities and excess volumes for four binary solution of ethyl acetate+toluene, ethyl acetate+ethyl benzene, ethyl acetate+carbon tetrachloride and ethyl acetate+chloroform at 303.15 K.

Experimental

Ethyl acetate (B.D.H. AnalaR), ethyl benzene (Fluka AG), toluene (AnalaR), carbon tetrachloride B.D.H. (spectroscopic), chloroform (B.D.H. spectroscopic) were further purified by standard procedures given by Riddick and Bunger³. All these chemicals were fractionally distilled just before use. Ethyl benzene (Fluka AG) of purity > 99% was used as received. The purity of the purified liquids were checked by measuring refractive indices at 303.15 K which agreed well with the literature values^{3,4}. The densities were measured with the help of a pycnometer having a bulb volume 11 cm³ approximately, calibrated against water and benzene. The apparatus used and the procedure followed are described elsewhere⁵. The density data are correct to ± 0.0001 units. The temperature of the water thermostat was

TABLE 1—DENSITIES (d) AND EXCESS VOLUMES (V^E) FOR ETHYL ACETATE+TOLUENE, + ETHYL BENZENE, + CARBON TETRACHLORIDE, + CHLOROFORM AT 303.15 K. X_1 IS THE MOLE FRACTION OF ETHYL ACETATE

X_1	d (g cm ⁻³)	V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)
(i) Ethyl acetate + toluene		
0.0	0.8577	—
0.0539	0.8592	+0.011
0.1609	0.8624	-0.003
0.3177	0.8673	-0.030
0.4188	0.8703	-0.025
0.5183	0.8736	-0.035
0.5723	0.8752	-0.040
0.6215	0.8766	-0.029
0.8586	0.8842	-0.025
0.9543	0.8872	-0.008
1.0	0.8885	—
(ii) Ethyl acetate + ethyl benzene		
0.0	0.8583	—
0.0533	0.8596	0.009
0.0979	0.8606	0.019
0.1926	0.8629	0.041
0.3714	0.8677	0.047
0.4541	0.8701	0.056
0.5748	0.8734	0.067
0.6533	0.8759	0.071
0.7279	0.8785	0.051
0.7991	0.8808	0.062
0.8661	0.8832	0.043
0.9336	0.8858	0.028
1.0	0.8885	—
(iii) Ethyl acetate + carbon tetrachloride		
0.0	1.5748	—
0.0667	1.5281	0.018
0.1673	1.4582	0.022
0.2628	1.3920	0.030
0.3959	1.3001	0.041
0.5679	1.1820	0.043
0.6611	1.1179	0.047
0.7657	1.0468	0.027
0.8641	0.9804	0.016
0.9263	0.9383	0.013
1.0	0.8885	—
(iv) Ethyl acetate + chloroform		
0.0	1.4706	—
0.0548	1.4328	-0.043
0.1407	1.3745	-0.058
0.2285	1.3170	-0.068
0.3553	1.2370	-0.049
0.4476	1.1813	-0.023
0.5145	1.1423	-0.007
0.5486	1.1226	+0.010
0.6163	1.0847	+0.024
0.6550	1.0694	+0.036
0.7302	1.0233	+0.026
0.7658	1.0047	+0.023
0.8425	0.9655	+0.022
1.0	0.8885	—

maintained at 303.15 \pm 0.02 K. The densities of purified liquids were in close agreement with the literature data^{3,4}. Mixtures were prepared by weighing the liquids in ground stoppered weighing flasks on a Metler (MERA-WAG-GDANSK, Poland) balance, accurate to 10⁻⁵ g.

* Author for correspondence.